

Akademios Learning Athletic Club UK-USA

Covaci Carla

06.01.2025

7-Day Meal Menu (with portions)

Sunday

Breakfast: Whole-milk fruit yogurt 168 g, Banana 100 g, Corn flakes 56 g

Lunch: Grilled chicken breast 132 g, Cooked white rice 158 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Cucumber 52 g

Dinner: Cooked carp fish 123 g, Boiled potatoes 180 g, Spanish steak skewers with saffron rice & yogurt sauce 56 g

Snacks: Orange 131 g, Pancakes 100 g, Honey 28 g, Milk chocolate 14 g

Monday

Breakfast: Hard-boiled eggs 2 × 50 g, White bread 2 slices × 29 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Raw carrots 50 g

Lunch: Chicken noodle soup (dry mix, prepared) 74 g, Cooked lean chicken breast 85 g, Multigrain bread 28 g

Dinner: Cooked pasta 200 g, Canned tuna in oil (drained) 146 g, Swiss cheese 28 g

Snacks: Pears 140 g, Plain whole-milk yogurt 113 g, Blueberries 56 g

Tuesday

Breakfast: Whole-milk fruit yogurt 168 g, Corn flakes 56 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Feta cheese 56 g, Raw carrots 72 g, Olives 12 g

Lunch: Grilled chicken breast 132 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Cucumber 52 g, Mashed potatoes 229 g

Dinner: White fish salad 150 g, Polenta (cooked) 150 g

Snacks: Banana 101 g, Jam 72 g, Whole-grain pancakes 148 g

Wednesday

Breakfast: Hard-boiled eggs 2 × 50 g, White bread 2 slices × 29 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Raw carrots 50 g

Lunch: Chicken noodle soup (dry mix, prepared) 74 g, Cooked lean chicken breast 85 g, Multigrain bread 28 g

Dinner: Cheese & vegetable thin-crust pizza 149 g

Snacks: Tangerine 88 g, Low-fat fruit yogurt 170 g

Thursday

Breakfast: Whole-milk fruit yogurt 168 g, Corn flakes 56 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Feta cheese 56 g, Raw carrots 72 g, Olives 12 g

Lunch: Grilled chicken breast 132 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Cucumber 52 g, French fries 200 g

Dinner: Polenta (cooked) 150 g, Swiss cheese 56 g, Sour cream 100 g

Snacks: Banana 101 g, Apples 125 g

Friday

Breakfast: Hard-boiled eggs 2 × 50 g, White bread 2 slices × 29 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Raw carrots 72 g

Lunch: Chicken noodle soup (dry mix, prepared) 74 g, Cooked lean chicken breast 85 g, Multigrain bread 28 g

Dinner: Swiss cheese 28 g, Fish with tomato-based sauce 100 g, Cooked pasta shells 210 g

Snacks: Strawberries 27 g, Kiwi 69 g, Pancakes 200 g, Honey 100 g

Saturday

Breakfast: Whole-milk fruit yogurt 168 g, Tomatoes 123 g, Feta cheese 56 g, Raw carrots 72 g, Olives 12 g, Muesli 66 g, Nuts 28 g

Lunch: Chicken cabbage rolls 3 pieces (200 g), Polenta 120 g

Dinner: Polenta (cooked) 150 g, Fish with tomato-based sauce 100 g

Snacks: Orange 131 g, Low-fat fruit yogurt 170 g